

Molecular Adsorption and Ion-exchange of Carboxylic Acids by Heteroionic Resins

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Molecular adsorption and ion-exchange of carboxylic acids (C_2 to C_4) on heteroionic resins, $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} H \\ Na \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ -resin, $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} H \\ K \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ -resin, and $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} Na \\ K \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ -resin, have been investigated. The cation-exchanger, Amberlite-IR-120, was saturated with two kinds of ions at three different mutual degrees of saturation. All the three acids are most strongly adsorbed by the potassium form; the order being $R-K > R-H > R-Na$. It is found that, the highest ion-exchange takes place from acetic acid and least from *n*-butyric acid. For all the three acids, Na^+ ion is more readily released than K^+ ion from their corresponding salt forms of the resin. The total ion-exchange from the heteroionic resin, $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} Na \\ K \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ -resin, is greater than from purely sodium form or from purely potassium form of the resin. The ion-exchange curves show maxima between 25% and 50% of potassium ion in the heteroionic $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} Na \\ K \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ -resin.

SYNTHETIC ion-exchange resins have the property of simultaneous ion-exchange and molecular adsorption, specially with weak electrolytes. Starobinets and Gleim¹, for the first time, investigated in some detail the differentiation between ion-exchange and molecular adsorption using carboxylic fatty acids with anion-exchange resins in chloride forms. In our previous communications^{2,3}, the results of study on ion-exchange and molecular adsorption with both cation-exchange as well as anion-exchange resins were reported. As electrolytes, some carboxylic acids and their different salts were used. The ion-exchange resins were also used in their different salt forms containing a single species of exchangeable ions.

The exchangeability of an ion from a heteroionic exchanger has been studied by many workers^{4,5}, using clay materials containing two different species of exchangeable ions. The work was extended by Pochhali⁷ to synthetic ion-exchange resins, both cationic and anionic, in their heteroionic forms where two different species of exchangeable ions were introduced into the resins. Uptil now, no attempt has been made to investigate the simultaneous ion-exchange and molecular adsorption from weak electrolytes with heteroionic ion-exchanger containing two different species of exchangeable ions.

In this paper, the results of the study on the molecular adsorption and the ion-exchange of carboxylic fatty acids by heteroionic cation-exchange resins, $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} H \\ Na \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ -R, $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} H \\ K \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ -R, $\left\{ \begin{smallmatrix} Na \\ K \end{smallmatrix} \right\}$ -R, with different degrees of saturation have been presented.

Experimental

Highly acidic cation-exchange resin, Amberlite-IR-120, a sulphonated polystyrene resin with 8% DVB, of the hydrogen form was saturated with two kinds of cations at three different degrees of saturation. The method of preparations of these kinds of resins has been described by Pochhali⁷.

The hydrogen form of the resin with known moisture content and known exchange capacity (4.90 ± 0.04 meq/gm dry resin) was used for the preparation of the heteroionic resins.

Acetic, propionic and *n*-butyric acids of "AnalaR grades" were used for the investigations.

The experiments were done at room temperatures ($30^\circ \pm 2^\circ$). Weighed amounts (about 1 gm) of the air-dried resin of known moisture content were

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TABLE 1

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{H} \\ \text{Na} \end{array} \right\} \text{—Resin}$$

Acids		Degree of saturation in percentage of total cations in the resin				
		H : 100 Na : 0	H : 78.5 Na : 21.5	H : 57 Na : 48	H : 35.5 Na : 64.5	H : 0 Na : 100
Acetic :	Adsorption	0.280	0.216	0.190	0.170	0.142
	Exchange	0	0.067	0.119	0.184	0.300
Propionic :	Adsorption	0.240	0.246	0.240	0.250	0.240
	Exchange	0	0.059	0.101	0.156	0.280
<i>n</i> -butyric :	Adsorption	0.295	0.286	0.287	0.295	0.274
	Exchange	0	0.048	0.098	0.148	0.294

Both adsorption and exchange values are given in meq/gm. dry resin.

TABLE 2

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{H} \\ \text{K} \end{array} \right\} \text{—Resin}$$

Acids		Degree of saturation in percentage of total cations in the resin				
		H : 100 K : 0	H : 76.3 K : 23.7	H : 51.5 K : 48.5	H : 27.6 K : 72.4	H : 0 K : 100
Acetic	Adsorption	0.280	0.245	0.280	0.270	0.280
	Exchange	0	0.022	0.086	0.209	0.288
Propionic	Adsorption	0.240	0.273	0.295	0.290	0.308
	Exchange	0	0.021	0.068	0.185	0.244
<i>n</i> -butyric	Adsorption	0.295	0.390	0.370	0.372	0.392
	Exchange	0	0.015	0.068	0.162	0.232

Both adsorption and exchange values are given in meq/gm. dry resin.

TABLE 3

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{Na} \\ \text{K} \end{array} \right\} \text{—Resin}$$

Acids		Degree of saturation in percentage of total cations in the resin				
		Na : 0 K : 100	Na : 25 K : 75	Na : 50 K : 50	Na : 75 K : 25	Na : 100 K : 0
Acetic :	Na ⁺ exchange	0	0.088	0.250	0.384	0.300
	K ⁺ exchange	0.288	0.284	0.220	0.120	0
	Total exchange	0.288	0.367	0.470	0.454	0.300
	Adsorption	0.280	0.286	0.200	0.170	0.142
Propionic	Na ⁺ exchange	0	0.079	0.184	0.264	0.280
	K ⁺ exchange	0.244	0.248	0.202	0.102	0
	Total exchange	0.244	0.327	0.386	0.366	0.280
	Adsorption	0.308	0.290	0.278	0.262	0.240
<i>n</i> -butyric :	Na ⁺ exchange	0	0.078	0.176	0.254	0.294
	K ⁺ exchange	0.232	0.260	0.176	0.087	0
	Total exchange	0.232	0.338	0.352	0.341	0.294
	Adsorption	0.392	0.366	0.330	0.304	0.274

Both adsorption and exchange values are given in meq/gm. dry resin.

equilibrated with 50 ml of acid solutions of known concentration. After equilibrium the clear solutions were analysed for estimation of ions (i.e., Na⁺ and K⁺) and the acids in the equilibrium solutions.

The initial and equilibrium concentrations of the acids were found out by alkalimetric titrations with standard sodium hydroxide solutions using phenolphthalein indicator. The concentrations of

Na⁺ and K⁺ ions in equilibrium solutions were found out by means of a Flame Photometer^s ("EEL"), using appropriate filters for sodium and potassium.

Results and Discussion

With all the heteroionic resins for each degree of saturation, molecular adsorption and ion-exchange

(both in meq/gm dry resin) of the three carboxylic acids, acetic, propionic and *n*-butyric were measured at different equilibrium concentrations. These values were plotted against equilibrium concentrations of the acids. To study the variation of adsorption and ion-exchange with degree of saturation of the heteroionic resins, some particular equilibrium concentration for the acids was chosen. As most of the experiments were performed with the equilibrium concentrations ranging from 0 to 1.0 eqv/litre, the results are taken conveniently at equilibrium concentration of 0.5 eqv/litre. For this equilibrium concentration, molecular adsorption and ion-exchange of the acids were computed from the corresponding graphs. The results are tabulated in Tables 1 to 3 and presented graphically in Figures 1, 2, 3 respectively.

Comparing the adsorption of the acids on the three homoionic resins, it is found that all the three acids are most strongly adsorbed by the potassium form, the order being $R-K > R-H > R-Na$ (Tables 1 and 2). Also it is found from Table 3, that, for all the three acids, Na^+ ion is more readily released than K^+ ion from their corresponding salt forms of the resin. This shows that K^+ ion is more strongly held than Na^+ ion by the resin. This indicates, that more strongly a counter-ion is held by the resin, stronger is the adsorption of the acids by that form of the resin.

Regarding the adsorption behaviour of the heteroionic resin, it is observed that, $\left. \begin{matrix} Na \\ K \end{matrix} \right\} - resin$ behaves quite differently from $\left. \begin{matrix} H \\ Na \end{matrix} \right\} - resin$ and $\left. \begin{matrix} H \\ K \end{matrix} \right\} - resin$. As has been mentioned above, that, for all the three acids, the adsorption is higher by the pure potassium form than the pure sodium form of the resin, the adsorption of the acids (as found from Fig. 3) increases almost linearly with increase in percentage of K^+ ion in the heteroionic $\left. \begin{matrix} Na \\ K \end{matrix} \right\} - resin$.

But it is not so for $\left. \begin{matrix} H \\ Na \end{matrix} \right\} - resin$ and $\left. \begin{matrix} H \\ K \end{matrix} \right\} - resin$. It is only in case of acetic acid with $\left. \begin{matrix} H \\ Na \end{matrix} \right\} - resin$, the

adsorption decreases regularly with increase in percentage of Na^+ ion in the resin (Fig. 1). But in other cases, no regularity is found in the variation of adsorption with the degree of saturation of exchangeable ions. With $\left. \begin{matrix} H \\ K \end{matrix} \right\} - resin$, the adsorption of all the three acids (acetic, propionic, *n*-butyric), at first increases regularly from pure $R-H$ upto about 50% of K^+ ion, afterwards adsorption has no tendency to increase, rather decreases, specially for acetic and propionic acids (Fig. 2). Similarly with $\left. \begin{matrix} H \\ Na \end{matrix} \right\} - resin$, the adsorp-

Fig. 1. $\left. \begin{matrix} H \\ Na \end{matrix} \right\} R + \text{Carboxylic acid}$
(a) Adsorption (b) Exchange
1. Acetic (○) 2. Propionic (●) 3. *n*-butyric (Δ)

Fig. 2. $\left. \begin{matrix} H \\ K \end{matrix} \right\} R \text{ Carboxylic acid}$
(a) Adsorption (b) Exchange
1. Acetic (○) 2. Propionic (●) 3. *n*-butyric (Δ)

tion of propionic and *n*-butyric acids, at first, increases with the percentage of H^+ ion in the resin, and then with further increase in the percentage of H^+ ion, there is a tendency to decrease (Fig. 1).

It is found from Figures 1, 2, 3 that, in all the heteroionic resins the highest ion-exchange takes place from acetic acid, then from propionic acid and least from *n*-butyric acid. Considering the dissociation constants⁹ of the acids, the position of *n*-butyric acid should have been between acetic and propionic acids. Here, the greater chainlength of

Fig. 3. $\left. \begin{matrix} \text{Na} \\ \text{K} \end{matrix} \right\} \text{R} + \text{Carboxylic acid}$
 (a) Total Ion-exchange, (b) Adsorption
 1. Acetic (○, ●) 2. Propionic (△, ▲)
 3. n-butyric (□, ■)

n-butyric acid masks the effect of dissociation constant and so ion-exchange is least in its case.

In the cases of $\left. \begin{matrix} \text{H} \\ \text{Na} \end{matrix} \right\} - \text{resin}$ and $\left. \begin{matrix} \text{H} \\ \text{K} \end{matrix} \right\} - \text{resin}$, as is expected, the ion-exchange increases with the degree of saturation with respect to the exchangeable ions in the resins (Figures 1 and 2). But $\left. \begin{matrix} \text{Na} \\ \text{K} \end{matrix} \right\} - \text{resin}$

shows an interesting behaviour regarding the total ion-exchange (Fig. 3). The total ion-exchange from the heteroionic resin is greater than from purely sodium form or from purely potassium form. The ion-exchange curves show maxima and it is found that the maxima lie between 25% and 50% of potassium ion in the heteroionic resins for all the three acids.

References

1. G. L. STAROBINETS and I. F. GLEIM, *Russ. J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **39**, 1166.
2. L. POCHHALI, S. K. ADHIKARY and K. C. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 859; 1977, **54**, 889; 1978, **55**, 366.
3. K. C. RAY, L. POCHHALI and S. K. ADHIKARY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 927.
4. L. WIKLANDER, *Ann. Royal Agr. Coll. Sweden*, 1946, **14**, 1.
5. S. K. MUKHERJEE, *Bull. Ind. Soc. Sc. Soil.*, 1942, **4**, 1; 1944, **6**, 19.
6. A. K. GANGULI and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1952, 56.
7. L. POCHHALI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 521; 1960, **37**, 527.
8. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd edn. (Longmans Green & Co., London), 1971.
9. R. C. WEST, "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics" (The Chemical Rubber Co., Ohio), 1971-72.